

MALE PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS IN EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION: MOTIVATIONS AND CHALLENGES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 32

Issue 4

Pages: 456-470

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3072

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14898017

Manuscript Accepted: 01-22-2025

Male Pre-Service Teachers in Early Childhood Education: Motivations and Challenges

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the motivations and challenges of Male Pre-Service Teachers in Early Childhood Education Program in Western Mindanao State University. The researchers conducted a one-on-one interview with five (5) Male Pre-Service Teachers. The findings of this study shed light on the motivations and challenges faced by Male Pre-Service Teachers in Early Childhood Education Program. Participants articulated various reasons for the motivations enrolling in the program such as influence by family, building self-reliance, and a passion for teaching young children for lifelong learning. Despite initial reservations, many participants found fulfillment in their roles as educators. However, the Pre-Service Teachers also encountered unique challenges, such as gender stereotypes and classroom management, which the Pre-Service Teacher navigated with perseverance and support. This study recommends that Male Pre-Service Teachers to actively engage in mentorship programs and seek support from peers, mentors, and family members. Foster a gender-inclusive environment in early childhood education to combat biases and stereotypes, promoting the value of male educators.

Keywords: *male pre-service teacher, early childhood education, influence, motivations, challenges*

Introduction

Teaching is a profession that comes with a lot of responsibility and duty towards students. Teachers encourage and motivate students to make important choices in life, share knowledge and educate. Beyond the transfer of academic knowledge, teachers serve as mentors, motivators, and role models, instilling values, fostering critical thinking, and nurturing social and emotional skills.

Men are perceived as being uncommon in the early childhood care and education sector. Men make up just 3.2% of ECE and kindergarten instructors nationwide, and 44% of them decide to quit their careers in less than five years. Men are discouraged from pursuing careers in early childhood education for a variety of reasons, such as rigid gender roles, the perception that early childhood education (ECE) is a low-status profession with poor compensation and benefits, and concerns from colleagues and families who wonder why men would be interested in working with young children (Manning up for Men: Recruitment and Retention in the Early Childhood Field, 2023).

There is a significant proof that many guardians or parents worry when their young children are assigned to male teachers. Men are expected to fulfill normative gender roles, and to be acutely aware of the risk of allegation of child sexual abuse as they enter the teaching profession, particularly in the early years. Male teachers feel that they are distrusted and under a lot of pressure at work due to these expectations. As a result, some students either drop out of the program or doesn't have the courage to take early childhood education (Yang Yang, 2018)

Despite of the challenges faced by the male pre-service teachers, there are still numerous students who want to enroll in this program. Many factors have been examined in an attempt to find which ones promote teacher motivation. Studies have shown that there are three basic kinds of teacher motivation that drives individuals to pursue a career, namely, extrinsic, intrinsic, and altruistic. Extrinsic motivations might involve factors like the salary structure and the amount of free time for family due to holidays. On the other hand, those driven by intrinsic motivations often seek continuous learning opportunities and strive for roles that match their skills and abilities. Altruistically motivated individuals seek personal fulfillment. These individuals are driven by their affection for children and their desire to make a difference in the students' lives (Saleem et al., 2021).

There is only few research regarding the lack of male teachers in early childhood education, because some think that male early childhood teachers are not capable of handling children and don't know how to discipline and manage the behavior of the child. This study will be conducted at the College of Teacher Education, Western Mindanao State University. For these reasons, the researchers would aim to know the reasons why there are only a few male educators in early childhood education.

Many research studies have investigated the motivation faced by male pre-service educators in early childhood education. However, few studies focus on the challenges encountered by male students in this program. Therefore, this study aims to fill this gap by investigating the challenges that the male students face as they prepare to become teachers.

Research Questions

This study attempted to determine the motivation and challenges of male pre-service teachers in early childhood education. Specifically, this study attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What motivated the male pre-service teacher to enroll in the early childhood education program?
2. What are the challenges encountered by the male pre-service teachers in the early childhood education program? What are the

strategies of ECE teachers to address the challenges in integrating stories in teaching Mathematics?

Literature Review

Male Pre-Service Teachers

According to the United States Bureau of Labor Statistics (2019), The proportion of male preschool and kindergarten teachers has remained below 3%, a trend that has not altered in recent years.

Best Male preschool teachers can be an excellent example to young kids, particularly boys. They engage in a lot of physical activities, to be in contrast to female preschool teachers who prefer peaceful games and strict regulations. (Besnard & Letarte, 2017).

Xu and Waniganayake (2018), discovered a shortage of non-Western men in early childhood education, nations such as in China, wherein, about 2% of ECE teachers are male. Nothing differs in the Philippines, where women outnumber males as educators in early childhood education. Shpancer et al. (2019), investigated male caregiver attitudes in childcare positioning and discovers that prejudices from society prevented men from participating in childcare job.

Motivation for Pursuing Teaching as a Career

Motivation refers to internal drive and desire that compels a person to engage in work and activities. It encompasses one's emotions, aspirations, and desires that influence their actions (Gul et al., 2020). Intrinsic motivations refer to the inner drive that leads individuals to engage in a behavior because they find satisfaction in the activity itself, rather than seeking external rewards or specific outcomes. Intrinsic motivations occur when we participate in an activity purely for enjoyment or to explore, learn, and develop our abilities. Autonomy, purpose and mastery are the key components of intrinsic-motivations.

When individuals have the freedom to act independently, feel that their efforts are meaningful and experience fulfillment from improving their skills, they are likely to be intrinsically motivated. In contrast, extrinsic motivation involves engaging in a behavior to obtain external rewards or avoid punishment (Cherry, 2022).

Furthermore, extrinsic motivation refers to the motivation that stems from exterior rewards. These kinds of rewards can be visible, like currency or status, or untouchable, such as compliment or recognition. Whereas intrinsic desire, which originates from inside, extrinsic desire is exclusively motivated by external incentives. Individuals who are extrinsically motivated will continue to participate in a task even if it does not bring intrinsic satisfaction. Extrinsic motivation is often associated with operant conditioning, where behavior is influenced by rewards or consequences (Cherry, 2023). Lastly, Altruistic motives involve seeing teaching as a valuable and socially beneficial profession, as well as having desire to support children's development and make a positive impact on society (Bergmark et al., 2018).

a). Self-Discovery

Self-discovery in student teachers involves exploring personal reflection and self-awareness to improve their self-perception, teaching methods, and professional development (Studers, 2017).

Three interdependent factors predominate, intrinsic motivations bound up with a sense of the inner life, the self and the quest for fulfilment and purpose; a desire to sustain an engagement with their chosen subjects and the opportunity to work with young people as part of the broader social project of education. Many studies have explored the appeal of teaching for potential teacher education students, pre-service teachers at the commencement, during and at the completion of their formal preparation, and practising teachers (Hammond, 2005).

According to Carneiro (2003), suggests that teaching, at its essence, is about self-discovery, authenticity, and fostering connections. The desire to teach arises from within, from the heart where intellect, emotions, and spirit intertwine. This enduring appeal of teaching is rooted in the individual's inner world, their search for meaning through ideas, relationships, and hope, all of which are crucial for effective teaching and learning. Educational institutions, like schools, serve as a space where students and teachers, as "travelers in the world of knowledge," seek meaning and significance in their shared journey.

b). Influenced by Family

According to Hui and Lent (2018), there is a considerable correlation between family impact and professional improvement, with young people experiencing greater support in tandem with greater professional improvement. Family support has been demonstrated to be a key component in the expectation of professional outcomes (Isik, 2021). Research indicates that a rise in the perceived social support from parents has a good impact on the process of choosing professional decisions (Kracke, 1997). Family has an unquestionable impact on a child's development, character formation, and career processes, among other things (Cui & Liu, 2019).

Challenges in the Chosen Career

a). Gender Stereotypes

Such beliefs are formed from the peoples' observations of the behavior of men and women in different social roles (Priyashantha et al.,

2021). Particularly, when women or men demonstrate certain behavior more typical to different social roles more often than the opposite sex, such behaviors are believed to be the common traits relevant to men or women (Eagly et al., 2020; Eagly and Karau, 2002). Hence, men are believed to be assertive, independent, rational and decisive, while women are believed to be showing concern for others, warmth, helpfulness and nurturance (Hoyt et al., 2009). These attributes concerning men and women are referred to as agentic masculine and communal feminine, respectively (Abele, 2003).

Furthermore, the problem with gender stereotypes is that precisely because they are general beliefs, over-generalization, they frequently lead to gender discrimination. People are treated unjustly by others, because these others are led by gender stereotypical beliefs instead of basing their acts on facts that are true and correspond to the individual case (Kite et al., 2008).

According to Moosa and Bhana (2019), men who choose to pursue a career in primary teaching experience a paradoxical situation where they are both feminized and positioned as “sexual initiators or aggressors”. This means that despite entering a profession that is traditionally associated with femininity, male primary teachers may face societal expectations that view them as potential threats or sources of sexual misconduct.

Furthermore, according to Ahmad et al., (2018), Gender equality have highlighted the significance of having both female and male teachers in early childhood education. One widely recognized benefit of male preschool teachers is that they provide children with the necessary experiences for a comprehensive education.

In China, there is a common societal expectation for male kindergarten teachers to serve as a role model and demonstrate socially accepted behaviors associated with masculinity. This expectation aims to provide male with early exposure to positive examples of how to embody masculinity, influencing their understanding and adoption of gender norms (Yang & McNair, 2019). Societal expectations are influenced by a political backdrop, where the Chinese central government is making efforts to discourage the perception of male as “feminized” (Zhang, 2021).

b.) Classroom Management

In the study of Brophy (1985), Classroom management defined here as the ability to establish, maintain, and restore the classroom as an effective environment for teaching and learning, is basic to general effectiveness as a teacher. This is especially true for teachers working in urban schools serving primarily lower socioeconomic status and minority group students, where potential management problems tend to be more numerous and intense.

According to Carol Read (2023), Classroom management is the backbone of effective primary teaching. If you're not able to manage your class, nothing seems to go right. If your classroom management is effective, everything else seems to fall into place. The main aim of classroom management with children is to create a happy, relaxed working atmosphere in which the norms and parameters of behavior are respected. Children feel secure and supported by the teacher, at the same time as they are helped to become increasingly independent in the way they approach their learning.

c.) Perception of Male Teachers

According to Robert (2021), Less than 2 percent of early childhood classroom teachers are men. The experiences of male teachers were investigated in this study, ranging from career exploration to classroom instruction. Finding the factors that challenge teachers' decisions to enter the profession of early childhood education was one of the study's goals. Perceptions and assumptions about male teachers, had biggest impact on their desire to stick around. In addition to offering light on involvement in an engaging classroom, study participants recognized critical qualities of a successful early childhood educator, both as a professional colleague and as a teacher. The charge to change the language of the child care profession and recognized that a teacher of early childhood is a professional, a role model, uses play for learning, and is not doing women's work.

In the study of Sumsion (2000), the views of a group of male pre-service early childhood educators about the possible benefits and drawbacks of choosing a non-traditional career path, as well as the gender-related conflicts they experienced during their pre-service training. Despite their hopes that their work in early childhood education will help bring about long-term gender reform, these men's testimonies revealed that they were all unable to articulate a coherent viewpoint on gender and issues related to gender. The participation and retention rates of pro-feminist males with potential to contribute to gender reform, as well as the necessity for early childhood teacher education programs to address gender issues.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive method. The idea that qualitative research was based on the perceptions and expectations of quality, while quality meant different things to different people (Aspers & Core, 2019). The study aimed to determine male pre-service teachers' motivation and challenges in early childhood education through one-on-one interviews with the respondents to gather data regarding the current state of affairs. Hence, the study focused on the motivations and challenges of early childhood male pre-service educators.

The data that was collected was described thoroughly using a qualitative style. It was a deliberate process that involved obtaining,

evaluating, and categorizing, and tabulating data regarding the state of affairs, prevailing views, procedures, trends, and cause-and-effect linkages. Subsequently, sufficient and precise interpretations of the data were made using statistical methods. Smaller yet targeted samples were required, and the data from these samples were categorized into patterns that served as the main framework for organizing and reporting the results.

Respondents

This study used purposive sampling in selecting respondents to attain precise answers to the interview questions. The five (5) Male Pre-service Early Childhood Teachers from the Western Mindanao State University, College of Teacher Education were included. Due to the limited number of male pre-service enrollees in the course, the researcher included 100% of them. Only third-year and fourth-year male pre-service teachers with face-to-face modality of education were part of the study. The identities of the respondents remained anonymous for concerns of personal privacy

In order to select respondents for the study, specific criteria were established. The researchers aimed to include male pre-service teachers who were in their third or fourth year of study at the College of Teacher Education. This ensured that the selected respondents had sufficient knowledge and experience in the field of teaching. Availability was also considered, as the researchers wanted to ensure that the selected respondents were willing and able to participate within the specified timeframe. To ensure a comprehensive understanding of the research topic, the researchers aimed for diversity in the selected respondents, considering factors such as background, experiences, and perspectives. The sample size was determined to be five male pre-service teachers, based on the scope and objectives of the study. The researchers employed purposive sampling, intentionally selecting participants who aligned with the specific criteria and purpose of the study. Informed consent was obtained from the selected respondents, ensuring that they understood the purpose of the study and the procedures involved. Overall, these criteria and methods were used to carefully select a representative and willing group of respondents for the study.

Instrument

This study utilized a qualitative methodology. Individual interviews were used in the study. The researcher aimed to determine the motivations and challenges of the Male Pre-service Teacher in Early Childhood Education at the College of Teacher Education. A semi-structured interview was used as the main data gathering for this study. This semi-structured interview consisted of (2) parts with a total of (6) items. The first part consisted of (3) questions that covered the motivation of Male Pre-service Teachers. The next part consisted of (3) items that covered the challenges encountered in the program by the target respondents. Furthermore, an audio recorder was utilized to ensure the spoken conversation was comprehensive and to provide a reliability test.

The semi-structured interview questions developed by the researchers were subjected to validation. This was validated by the research experts of the College of Teacher Education at Western Mindanao State University. A content validation sheet was given along with the letter asking for a favor to validate the research instrument.

The semi-structured interview developed by the researchers is the subject of the reliability test. This underwent a reliability test, which was done through pilot testing. The pilot testing was intended to ensure that the procedures and techniques used for this study's data collection were appropriate and consistent. There were two (3) Male Pre-service Teachers in Early Childhood Education who volunteered to participate in the pilot testing.

Procedure

The following guidelines served as a guide for the researchers when conducting the interview:

Securing consent before conducting the study. In order to conduct face-to-face interviews with the chosen respondents for the study, the researchers drafted and submitted a formal letter that had been approved by their research instructor. Another letter was also given to the respondents ahead of time, which was also approved by the researcher instructor, to ask permission to conduct a study at their convenience.

Conduct of Personal Interview. A proper setting was chosen where the respondents were comfortable with the conduct of the interview. The open-ended interview is intended to fully explain the responses, and participants were guaranteed the privacy of their answers. In addition, to prevent incorrect assumptions, the participants were informed of the interview's objectives, expectations, and timeline. The interview was done in an informal manner, a conversational type, with the guide questions as a basis to allow the degree of freedom and adaptability in getting the information from the participants. The questions were asked one at a time, and there was ample time for the participants to think about or construct their answers to the questions given. The interview process, including conversations, was documented in writing to guarantee accurate data collection related to the interview.

Data Analysis

According to Elmansy (2023) identifying, examining, and interpreting patterns or themes in a dataset such as written texts, interview transcripts, or survey responses is possible through the use of thematic analysis, a qualitative research technique. In order to identify underlying meanings, ideas, and concepts, it includes systematically organizing and analyzing the data.

This study utilized a qualitative technique and a thematic approach to thoroughly examine the themes and variations identified by the data. The data gathered from male pre-service teachers' interviews regarding their motivation and challenges in early childhood education was used to conduct the analysis. To understand the motivation and challenges, the data was compiled, examined, and explained. The researchers transcribed the data that was gathered from the respondents during the interview. After transcribing the data, the researchers analyzed the codes in terms of the themes.

Ethical Considerations

For ethical concerns researchers acquired permission from the Dean of the College of Teacher Education and WMSU Research Ethics Committee Review, Board, complete approval to request permission to conduct this study. The respondents were given informed consent about the purpose, methods, and implications of the research.

The identity of the participant was kept confidential and used in the research. Personal information was not shared without the participant's consent during the interview. Before the interview process for the entire proceedings, the respondent's permission to be audio-tape recorded was asked.

Results and Discussion

This section shows the demographic data of the respondents, data collection and data analysis which involves treatment of data, summary of collected data and presentation of emerging themes from the respondents.

Table 1. Demographic Data of the Respondents

<i>Respondent's No.</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Year Level</i>
R1	21	4th
R2	22	4th
R3	22	4th
R4	20	3rd
R5	20	3rd

Table 1 shows the summary of demographic data of the respondents. The selected respondents came from the College of Teachers Education's Early Childhood Education program. Three (3) participants were from the fourth year, and the other two (2) participants were from the third year.

Data Collection Procedure

One-on-one interview was utilized in this study to gain a better understanding of the challenges and motivations faced by male preservice teachers in the field of Early Childhood Education programs who had their On-Campus Internship at Western Mindanao State University-Integrated Laboratory School (ILS). Five (5) respondents were chosen to be interviewed one-on-one for the data collection. Letters were given beforehand to the participants for their consent and the locations that would be most convenient for them before the interview.

Upon their approval, the researcher followed the scheduled time after getting their availability. Then, the researchers asked the participants for their consent to audio record the entire interview. Upon gaining the consent of the participants to audio record, the researchers proceeded with interviewing the participants. The interview session lasted for about 9–15 minutes. The audio recordings of the interview were transcribed afterwards.

Interview Findings

This study aimed to determine the motivations and challenges of male pre-service teachers in early childhood education. The responses of the respondents were transcribed, and themes were drawn and presented along with the research questions. Five (5) pre-service teachers were interviewed for this purpose. This section shows the demographic data of the respondents, data collection and data analysis which involves treatment of data, summary of collected data and presentation of emerging themes from the respondents.

Interview Interview Question 1. What inspired you to pursue a career in early childhood education?

Respondent's Responses

Two of the respondents (R2 and R3) have the same answer: they were inspired by their families and mother. One (1) of the respondents (R3) answered that he is inspired by his friends and believed in him that he can do it. One (1) of the respondents (R1) stated that he is inspired to pursue this career because he wants to educate people.

One (1) of the respondents stated that he is inspired to pursue this career because he loves to teach little kids. One (1) of the respondents (R5) answered that he pursues this career because he is curious about the development of a child so that he can understand their development. One (1) of the respondents (R4) answered that he had no choice and wasn't able to pursue his first choice.

“.....We are a family of teachers, my sisters are teachers my cousins almost all of them are professional teachers, that's why I choose this field, but I did not really choose in ECE....” R2

“...The first reason is my family, especially my mom, who encouraged me to pursue this...” R3

“...The second reason is my friends. Despite them saying that this is the most challenging course, they believed in me...” R3

“...Lastly, the third reason is my love for teaching little kids...” R3

“...Honestly speaking, this is not really my first choice. Unfortunately, due to some personal reasons, I wasn't able to pursue my first choice...” R4

“...I am curious about the development of a child. That is why I pursue this kind of course so that I can understand about their development...” R5

Researcher's Reflection

Based on the gathered responses by the researchers, it highlights the influence of family, friends, and personal interests in inspiring individuals to pursue specific careers. Family support, particularly from mothers, emerged as a common source of inspiration. The belief and encouragement of friends also played a motivating role.

Respondents expressed a commitment to making a positive impact on society and a genuine interest in their chosen fields. However, external factors sometimes limited career choices. These findings contribute to our understanding of the factors that drive career aspirations.

Interview Question 2. What experiences have influenced your decisions to pursue this program?

Respondent's Responses

PSTs described their experiences that influenced their decision to pursue this program. R5 said that one family member has a disability, and he is the one teaching her, he thinks that the development is slow, and he wants to know how the development of a child works. That's why he took this career.

“...I'm teaching a family member with a disability, and I noticed her slow development. That's why I'm taking this course, to understand why progress is slow. Along the way, I understand why it is that way...” R5

Researcher's Reflection

The PST's experiences provide important insights into the reasons why the respondents chose to pursue a career in early childhood education. These reflections highlight the importance of personal experiences and the desire to make a positive impact on children's growth and development as key factors that influenced their decision.

Interview Question 3. What do you find most attractive about working with young children?

Respondent's Responses

All of the PSTs (1, 2, 3, 4, 5) find it attractive to work with young children. One (1) of the respondents (R1) answered that children see you as their second parent, they rely on you, and later on, they can do things on their own because of your teachings. One (1) of the respondents (R2) said that young children have fresh minds and can instill good deeds in them when they are still young, and they will follow them. One (1) of the respondents (R3) answered that every detail you teach to children, they take it and apply it.

One (1) of the respondents (R4) said that children are innocent, unlike teenagers; children are very honest and curious, and they are true to themselves. One (1) of the respondents stated that, in order to capture children's attention, you need to develop a strategy to catch their attention and interest and also to develop themselves not only as students but also as individuals.

“...Oh, so I think the most attractive thing to experience or to see having an interaction with children is that they see you as their second parent. They rely on you...” R1

“...So, they have fresh minds, you can instill good deeds to them, good manners, they will not reason out. What you taught they follow it...” R2

“...Every detail that is given is highlighted, everything that is taught to them, they really take it then they also apply it...” R3

“...Their innocence. Unlike adults or teenagers, children are very honest. And also, their curiosity, they are real to themselves...” R4

“...About their behaviors and as well, how will you... develop or have your strategy to catch their attention, their interest, and also to develop themselves not only as a student but also as an individual...” R5

Researcher's Reflection

Based on the gathered responses by the researchers, PSTs highlight the appeal and share their attraction about working with young children. PSTs showcase the joy and fulfillment that comes from working with young children and the unique qualities they possess.

Interview Question 4. Have you ever felt any bias or stereotypes directed towards you due to your choice of profession? Can you share some instances?

Respondent’s Responses

Most of the respondents (PST 1, 3, 4, and 5) felt bias or stereotypes towards their choice of profession being a male pre-service teacher. R1 answered that in tutoring children preferred female teachers. And male teachers are usually tasked with setting up events, which can be challenging for women. One (1) of the respondents stated, in the teaching profession, men are viewed as soldiers by children, and only women are good at it. R4 answered that some things that male teachers who appear to be educating kids are unable to accomplish because people believe that it is against the rules for them to do so. However, it's okay when the instructor is a woman. R5 stated that male teachers who are handling ECE classes are less common. So, it is mostly females. R2 didn't experience any bias or stereotypes towards their choice of profession.

“...Children prefer female teachers when it comes to tutoring because it is not only their choice, but it is also the choice of their parents because they believe that female teachers have more patience than men...” R1

“....Having an activity or event at school, Male teachers are the ones who are assigned to do the setup that is hard to do for women...” R1

“...Only women are good but men are not good when it comes to teaching and children see men as soldiers...” R3

“...There are certain things that male teachers cannot do because of the perception that are forbidden because they are male. But when it's a female teacher, it's okay. Because they are women ...” R4

“...Male teachers who are handling ECE classes are less common. So mostly females..” R5

“...I didn't experience those stereotypes, if you look at the field there are a lot of male teachers, and even in our department there are many male teachers,..” R2

Researcher’s Reflection

The respondents mentioned stereotypes or biases toward their choice of profession. PSTs highlighted that they felt biased because some people think that only women can teach, and children see men as soldiers. With this, the responses of the PSTs can be seen that they encountered those challenges as male pre-service teachers.

Interview Question 5. Can you share a specific challenge you have encountered as a male pre-service teacher in early childhood education, and how did you overcome it?

Respondent’s Responses

Most of the respondents (PST 1, 2 and 3) said that handling or managing the class was the most challenging that they have encountered as a male pre-service teacher in early childhood education. R1 answered that there's a limitation between a female learner and a male teacher. One (1) respondent stated that it was their first time to manage a class. R3 answered that by showing strategies on how to handle the class. Two respondents (2) didn't encounter challenges as a male pre-service teacher in early childhood education.

“...there's a limitation if there is an emergency. So, to avoid any issues or any problems or complaints coming from the student or the parents. So, we need the support of other PSTs, other female teachers...” R1

“...It was hard to be part of the practicum, first time practicing how to manage the class and how to deliver my lessons...” R2

“...Being a teacher has as many peaks as being a male teacher. That's why in instructional materials. I really overcome it, like I'm showing that I can also teach, I can handle kids, and also, I can share what I can do....” R3

Researcher’s Reflection

From the responses, it can be seen that the male pre-service teachers are challenged with how to handle or manage the classroom, so with the young children. Male pre-service teachers are also challenged with how to deal with little girls. Aside from that, the respondents were also challenged in doing instructional materials, wherein they saw that the females are more creative when it comes to visual aids. Through these challenges they encountered, they were getting some pieces of advice or help from mentors and fellow pre-service teachers to improve their chances of success in handling early childhood learners.

Table 2. Emergent Themes for Statement of the Problem 1

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subordinate Themes</i>	<i>Codes</i>
Intergenerational Interactions	Support Network	They were inspired by their parents and cousins.
	Influenced by family	That his mom was the one who gave it to him and that being a teacher
Holistic Development and Interaction	Lifelong Learning	One family member has a disability, and he is the one teaching her.
	Interactive Participation	They can do things on their own because of your teachings.
	Building Self Reliance	Easily catch their attention and interest.

Figure 1. *Emergent Themes for Statement of the Problem 1*

Relationship of Theme 1. Intergenerational Interactions

The Inter-generational Interaction

Refers to the process of interaction between members of different generations. It involves the exchange of values, life priorities, and ideologies among individuals from different age groups. The interaction is influenced by various factors such as socio-demographic, ethno-cultural, economic, and political aspects (Gafurovna et al., 2014)

“Just like what I've said earlier, when I was young, I used to take care of my young cousins. Through that, I was able to experience how to handle them and play with them...” (R4)

According to Hancock (2018), practices that bridges generations involved bringing the young and old to engage in worthwhile, comstructive activities to encourage deeper intergenerational understanding and respect. All things considered, engaging with other generations can be a wonderful approach to create partnerships, healthier people across the board, and more resilient communities.

Furthermore, intergenerational interaction is a potent instrument that can advance mutual respect, increase collective wisdom, and spark creativity. The idea is to use the distinct abilities and knowledge that every generation has to offer to build a society that is more tolerant, understanding, and flexible (Dpaulla et al., 2023).

Support Network

Maintaining relationships with your family and loved ones is equally crucial. A support network is a group of individuals you can trust to offer you encouragement, direction and assistance. In order to facilitate your goals, both personal and professional, you will have a strong support network that you can rely on through good times and bad. It's crucial to effectively leverage your support system to establish long-lasting relationships with the people in your life.

“First of all, we are a family of teachers, my sisters are teachers my cousins almost all of them are professional teachers...” (R2).

According to Clinic (2010), the support system consists of individuals such as friends, family members, and colleagues who offer both emotional and practical help. In educational settings, classmates, helpful staff members, and teachers can offer assistance, and as we progress in our professional lives, our colleagues can also serve as important sources of support

Building a strong support network is critical since it can include a wide range of interactions with different people who provide various types of assistance. In today's society, support networking and technology tools make communication easier, allowing us to interact quickly with a diverse group of people. However, it is also critical to establish deeper relationships and spend quality face-to-face time with folks who truly care about well-being. These interactions between people not only help to achieve balance but also greatly improve academic performance (Oregon State University, 2024).

Influenced by Family

Family impact adds to support, direction, and education, which can influence educational aspirations, professional choices, and personal ethics. A student's family plays a varied role in their academic journey, impacting not just their cerebral growth but also their social and emotional development.

“And one reason that influences me to pursue this course is that my mother and as well as my young cousins.” (R4)

According to Oklahoma State University (2014), the family is the most fundamental and significant social structure, playing a vital role in both an individual's life and the larger community. It is obvious how important families are to society as a whole. Children are more influenced by their families than by society or their peers, despite this. Family plays a very significant and crucial part in a child's

creativity as well as in cultural, social, and moral aspects of life.

Additionally, Int J Environ Res Public Health (2021), the parent's educational attainment, gender, and wealth as control factors, there was a significant correlation between academic satisfaction and family influence and happiness through self-efficacy in professional decisions. Career decision self-efficacy and contentment were significantly connected with family influence and academic fulfillment. Relationship between the career process and happiness and the work and support of students' families as well as academic fulfillment. It was acknowledged that a comprehensive approach encompassing education, work history, and family should be taken into account when evaluating career realities.

Relationships of Theme 2. Holistic Development and Interaction

The data gathered show that male PSTs in early childhood education are motivated in teaching in early childhood education because of the holistic development and interaction.

Holistic Development and Interaction

The holistic method aims to cultivate students who are analytical self-assured, and self-reliant, with a focus on transforming learning into a journey of self-enhancement that explicitly acknowledges both the individual and the social environment in the educational process. It acknowledges the importance of addressing the unique needs of each learner within the context of interaction, emphasizing that the social dynamics of this interaction play a crucial role.

This approach values the interactions that occur within this social setting as fundamental for nurturing critical thinkers, incorporating the experiential knowledge of both learners and educators to enhance the teaching environment and boost learners' levels of achievement (Patel, 2003).

"...You can see also that they are improving and that is based on the evaluation that you are giving them so you can see the scores of them that is also improving."(R1).

Additionally, a holistic approach is one that views a subject as a single, interrelated whole; it also entails seeing the wider picture, thinking beyond the box, and even taking the box totally out. To ensure the incorporation of varying viewpoints and thinking styles, this holistic approach integrates design and creative activities. It acknowledges the significance of the physical, emotional, cognitive, and spiritual dimensions of the individual, as well as the potential influence of design and design-oriented research within each of these realms (Craig, 2022).

Lifelong Learning

The process of continuously acquiring up new abilities, skills, and knowledge throughout one's life is known as lifelong learning. It is about maintaining your curiosity, flexibility, and open-mindedness at whatever age or under any given situation. Many methods exist for lifelong learning, such as self-directed study and formal education.

"It's like in my family because at the first time that I am teaching her because she has a disability or like not well, her development is not good."(R5)

According to Pantala (2022), lifelong learning is a personal reality that exists, learning and growth that people acquire through experiences they have had in a variety of contexts, as well as via relationships and activities they engage in throughout their lives.

The process of developing a person's personality is greatly aided by lifelong learning, which also helps in adapting to the constantly shifting demands of the workplace and the society in general. The importance of lifelong learning for a person's growth and the achievement of his or her potential both personally and professionally are established (Toxirovna, 2021).

Building Self-reliance

In order to successfully negotiate the demanding and frequently unpredictable world of education, male pre-service teachers must develop their sense of self-reliance. Male preservice teachers who practice self-reliance can acquire the independence and resiliency necessary to be successful in their positions.

"... I started to love this course because I was able to really understand children, especially when they are having problems and you can really expressive and using all those theories that the teacher taught you..." (R1)

Developing self-reliance will allow you to have confidence in your ability to rely on your inner resources to decide when to use them and when to seek assistance to lead a purposeful, happy life. By being self-reliant, you may conquer challenges, grow from mistakes, and improve your sense of confidence and self-worth (Whitener,2019).

Additionally, Kloppers (2014), self-reliance is the capacity to rely on oneself for one's needs, choices, and activities without unduly depending on other people for support or approval. The main advantages of self-reliance include improved self-confidence and self-esteem, more freedom, and stronger resilience in the face of adversity.

Interactive Participation

Engaging in interactive activities fosters diversity, cooperation, and the sharing of different viewpoints. It promotes creativity and innovation by enabling people to share their special knowledge and thoughts. Interactive involvement increases confidence in and dedication to the results by actively including participants in the decision-making and problem-solving processes.

“And when you interact with them, you don't need to pretend. You just need to deliver the things that they need, the things that you think that could help them to develop more...”(R4)

“About their behaviors and as well, how will you develop or have your strategy to catch their attention, their interest, and also to develop their selves not only as a student but also as an individual.”(R5)

Interactive participation involves engaging stakeholders in various processes, such as system design and filmmaking, to ensure their active involvement and contribution. This approach emphasizes the importance of including diverse voices and perspectives, as seen in the call for research diversity to encompass a wide range of contexts and experiences.

Table 3. Emergent Themes for Statement of the Problem 2

Superordinate Themes	Subordinate Themes	Codes
Gender stereotypes in the teaching profession	Role Expectations Perception of male teachers	Assignments of physical tasks Perceptions of men's capability
Classroom Management Challenges	Overcoming stereotypes Classroom management and teaching delivery	Using of instructional materials and proving they can handle the young children. Highlighted the importance of practicing, seeking advice from mentors

Relationship of Interview Responses to Research Question 2:

Statement of the Problem 2: What are the challenges encountered by the male pre-service teachers in the early childhood education program? (Refer to figure 2)

Figure 2. Themes of Research Question 2

Relationships of Theme 1: Gender stereotypes in Teaching Profession

The data gathered shows that male PSTs in early childhood education encountered gender stereotypes due to their chosen career. The responses are based on the challenges that male pre-service teachers in early childhood education have encountered.

Gender stereotypes in Teaching Profession

According to Brussino and McBrien (2022), gender stereotypes continue to exist in education and other domains despite progress in acknowledging that boys and girls, as well as women and men, are not limited by conventional roles. Gender stereotypes have an impact on children and young people from an early age, and peer, teacher, and parental influences can have an impact on how pupils internalize their gender identities. Therefore, in addition to pre-primary education intervention, primary and secondary education policies are essential for eradicating gender stereotypes and advancing gender equality.

Role Expectations

The majority of PST students stated that the challenges that they are facing is the role expectation of the society, if you are a male, you should do things that male usually do.

“...you will be prone to do or you are the one who is tasked to do all those heavy activities or heavy chores...” (R1)

“...why am I a teacher? They indicate that they see men as soldiers or engineers.” (R3)

“...When I say I'm early childhood educator, yes, they are questioning why. Because why am I not enrolled in crim and any boys track related...” (R5)

The idea of role expectations plays a crucial role in influencing social behavior. Studies have shown that these expectations can impact how individuals behave in different scenarios. For instance, role expectations can shape the way people engage with each other in settings like work or family (Kuriloff, 2009). Additionally, these expectations can affect how individuals assess their own performance within a specific role (Gibson & Vermeulun, 2003). Lastly, role expectations can also influence the expectations individuals hold for others in a particular social context (Fischer, 2006).

Primary school role difference frequently mirrors larger cultural gender conceptions that are coming under more and more scrutiny. However, educational settings haven't always been subjected to the same degree of scrutiny. Comprehending the origins and varieties of coping mechanisms will facilitate the creation of targeted treatments aimed at enhancing the retention rate of male primary educators (Cruickshank et al., 2020).

Perception of Male Teachers

Some of the PST student answered that one of the challenges that they are facing in early childhood education is the perception of male, if you are male teaching is not really for you.

“...but they're the choice of their parents also because they believe that female teachers have more patience than the man...” (R1)

“...there are certain things that they cannot do because of the perception that it is prohibited because they are male...” (R4)

Gender stereotypes about jobs and the attributes presumed to be necessary to do them underpin the perception that jobs are rarely gender neutral. Due to their deep ingrained cultural roots, gendered occupational stereotypes persist even in the face of an increase in the number of women adopting traditionally “male” occupations. Furthermore, despite repeated government endeavors, males are still underrepresented in traditionally “feminine” fields like teaching since these positions are still thought to be exclusively appropriate for people who exhibit certain “feminine” traits. Less than 15% of elementary school teachers in the United Kingdom (UK) are men. Therefore, it is crucial to de-stereotype this job role because the United Kingdom needs more trained teachers (Cruickshank et al., 2020; McDowell & Klattenberg, 2019).

Additionally, research has shown that, despite being underrepresented, male primary educators in minority groups are frequently expected to assume leadership positions in the fields of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics as well as jobs like sports coaching, manual labor, and disciplinarian (Cruickshank et al., 2020).

Relationships of Theme 2: Classroom Management Challenges

The information gathered indicates that because early childhood teaching was their chosen field, male PSTs in that field ran across gender prejudices. The answers are based on the difficulties that male pre-service educators in the field of early childhood education have faced. The PSTs are having the challenges in managing the class, as it says that management is a women work.

Classroom Management Challenges

According to Foster (2022), a teacher's efforts to establish and preserve a classroom climate that supports effective education are referred to as classroom management. By controlling students' expectations and behaviors, these acts include choices about the structure, organization, and activities of the course.

Overcoming Stereotypes

Overcoming stereotypes is one of the things that the PSTs has encounter in early childhood education, male teachers can challenge stereotypes and demonstrate that they are capable of effectively educating and engaging with students.

“So we really need to give the students a little or we need to need the support of other PSTs, other female teachers..” (R1)

“So, you really need to talk softly. You really need to talk in like how female teachers talk to their students. So, you really need to adjust...”(R1)

“..That's why in instructional materials. I really overcome it, like I'm showing that I can also teach, I can handle kids, and also, I can share what I can do.” (R3)

“I'm doing my best, doing everything that I could to show everyone, to show my classmates, the professors, and the people that surround me that being a male teacher is not just being a male teacher...” (R4)

The global teaching profession is becoming more and more female-dominated. In Poland, just 1% of early childhood educators and preschool teachers in Poland are men. Men who choose to work as kindergarten or primary school teachers must deal with attitudes, sentiments, and occasionally unfavorable gender stereotypes. Male teachers of children between the ages of three and six are frequently

the target of fear. Nevertheless, findings also suggest that male presence in the classroom has positive effects on children's development in particular domains. Given that, aside from students and teachers, male teachers are one of the most important educational issues, parents' perceptions of them are significant in this context (Koperna, 2019).

Even though women and men have nominal equal access to school, gender differences rather than gender equality nevertheless characterize educational and occupational trajectories. Women are typically employed in low-status roles in the health and social sectors, whereas men are overrepresented in STEM subjects and higher positions. Even after achievement is taken into account, females report lower academic self-concepts in STEM courses than boys, and the same is true for boys' self-concepts in reading and languages. These inequalities are already evident in the classroom. Gender disparities in education are thought to be mostly maintained by gender preconceptions propagated by socializing forces. Since teachers' attitudes and methods of instruction are recognized to have a significant impact on students' motivation and performance, they are crucial beginning points for the promotion of gender equality in education. In order to provide equal opportunities for boys and girls in coeducational environments, educators must examine their own gender prejudices. Additionally, they need to be knowledgeable on how to motivate all pupils, regardless of gender, by fostering their enthusiasm through teaching strategies and gender inequalities in education. However, there are few training programs that help instructors develop their competencies for reflective coeducation, and gender stereotypes are rarely addressed in regular teacher education (Marlene, 2020).

Classroom Management and Teaching Delivery

Classroom management refers to the strategies and techniques used by teachers to create a positive and productive learning environment. Some pre-service teachers may face difficulties in effectively managing the classroom.

"Maybe in your class management or the teaching itself? Being a male teacher, especially when you are teaching..." (R1)

"That's why it was hard during my first practicum, learning how to manage the class, how to deliver my lessons, and feeling a bit unsure at first, but I learned along the way..." (R2)

"So what I did was practice a lot and get some advice from our mentors. They were always there to help us, so I took their advice and applied it to my teaching. This way, the outcome would be good..." (R2)

Many teachers often list classroom management as a concern. A typical cause of these issues with classroom management is the teacher's inability to successfully engage pupils and build genuine relationships with them. When it comes to effectively engaging students and fostering authentic relationships, it is imperative to center Culturally Relevant Pedagogy, particularly for Culturally and Linguistically Diverse pupils who have been recognized as having Emotional Behavior Disorder (EBD). Essentially, educators should have high expectations for their pupils, a strong sense of self-efficacy, create and preserve real classroom communities, and exhibit a love of what they do. Regrettably, a lot of educators do not place enough emphasis on the necessity of researching their own cultural self-awareness or being culturally sensitive to the families of their pupils (William, 2021).

Moreover, due to lack of adequate guidance, instruction, and support provided by the educator training programs on essential and advanced techniques for effective classroom management, educators feel uneducated and unready to effectively prioritize these aspects to engage students successfully in the classroom (William, 2021)

Conclusions

Conclusion to Research Question 1

Based on the findings of this study conducted at Western Mindanao State University, it can be concluded that male pre-service teachers in early childhood education have diverse motivations for choosing this program. The participants in the study, who are studying to become teachers for young children, mentioned different factors that influenced their decision. Some mentioned being influenced by their parents who encouraged them to pursue a career in early childhood education. Others mentioned the support and encouragement they received from their family and friends.

Additionally, some participants mentioned that they chose this program due to limited options in other fields. However, personal reasons also played a significant role in their decision-making. They expressed a desire to educate others and a genuine enjoyment of working with young children, which brought them a sense of fulfillment. Despite not initially considering this program as their first choice, they developed a passion for teaching young children throughout their studies. Overall, this study highlights the multiple motivations that drive men to pursue a career in early childhood education.

Implications

The field of early childhood education will be affected in a number of ways by the study's conclusions. First off, by comprehending the various reasons why men choose to become pre-service teachers, educational institutions and policymakers can create recruitment tactics that entice more men to enter the field. One way to persuade males to choose a career in early childhood education is to emphasize the value of working with young children and the support and encouragement they receive from their parents.

Second, the results of the study highlight how crucial it is to give people who might not have initially made early childhood education their top priority chances and support. Educational institutions can attract a diverse pool of candidates and diversify their teaching staff by developing pathways and programs that address the needs of persons with limited options in other disciplines.

The study also emphasizes how important it is to follow one's own goals and a sincere desire to teach others while deciding whether to become an early childhood educator. This suggests that attracting and keeping male pre-service teachers depends on creating a feeling of fulfillment and purpose in the field. To foster and maintain this passion, educational institutions should offer professional development opportunities, mentorship programs, and a welcoming work atmosphere.

In summary, this study's results imply that the field of early childhood education can draw a more diverse workforce and eventually improve the quality of education for young children by comprehending and addressing the motives of male pre-service teachers.

Conclusion to Research Question 2

Based on research findings about the challenges that male pre-service teachers encounter in the early childhood education program, participants in this study mentioned a number of challenges they experienced. Some participants stated that whenever an event occurs at school, it is always the male pre-service teachers who are tasked with handling all of the heavy work, including the assignment of tangible tasks; however, they are unable to undertake certain tasks that they believe are forbidden because they are male. Furthermore, a participant noted that one of the challenges for male pre-service teachers is demonstrating their ability to use instructional tools and work with young students. Furthermore, some participants mentioned that the most difficult issue they have encountered is how to deal lecture in class

In conclusion with the challenges faced by male pre-service teachers in early childhood education programs. male pre-service teachers seek assistance from mentors and peers, and they practice extensively. To overcome these challenges and demonstrate their ability to supervise the education of young children, they emphasized the importance of practice and mentorship childhood program.

Implications

The research findings show that male pre-service teachers in early childhood education face gender stereotypes, like being given physical tasks and restricted from certain activities based on their gender. To create a fairer environment, it's important to challenge these stereotypes.

It's also important for male pre-service teachers to receive ongoing training in using teaching tools and working with young students to overcome these challenges. Mentorship and peer support play a crucial role in helping them navigate obstacles and improve their teaching skills.

By emphasizing practice, skill development, and seeking support, male pre-service teachers can overcome challenges and excel in educating young children. Institutions should promote inclusive policies, adjust curriculums, and provide a supportive atmosphere to empower male educators in early childhood education programs.

Through efforts to promote gender equality, mentorship, and skill enhancement, male pre-service teachers can successfully tackle the complexities of teaching and make meaningful contributions to the field of early childhood education.

Recommendation

Administrator. Provide effective alternative solutions to the difficulties, challenges, and queries of male pre-service teachers in early childhood education.

College of Teacher Education - College Student Council. Anticipated contributions to understanding the motivations and challenges of male preservice teachers in ECE. Insights into the support mechanisms and resources required to enhance the recruitment and retention of male preservice teachers in ECE programs and develop initiatives and programs that address the specific needs of male preservice teachers in ECE.

College of Teacher Education. Provide mentorship programs for male pre-service teachers. These programs can offer guidance and support, helping them to navigate the unique challenges they face. Provide a more gender-inclusive environment in early childhood education programs. This can be achieved by promoting the value of male educators in early childhood education and addressing any biases or stereotypes that may exist.

Mentors. Researchers recommend that mentors should constantly be willing to communicate with PSTs, especially when they are experiencing challenges. A mentor who is willing to listen, offer guidance, and assist the PSTs. Mentors can served as a positive role models for male pre-service teachers by sharing their own strategies in handling young children.

Family. Researchers recommend that families provide moral support, inspiration, and motivation to their children, particularly because they are teaching young children. Additionally, fostering open communication between male pre-service teachers and their families can create a supportive network that reinforces their passion for teaching and learning.

Pre-service Teachers. Pre-service teachers should help other PSTs so that they have a companion to lean on. They should believe in

themselves and seek suggestions from their mentors, peers, and family members.

Future Researchers. Future researchers could look deeper into the role of family and social influences on the career choices of male pre-service teachers. Understanding these influences could help in designing interventions to encourage more males to consider careers in early childhood education.

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